

Gender Inequality in Assamese Novel

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One is not born, but rather becomes women

Simone De Beauvoir

Abstract:

Men and women are two human beings, but the patriarchal society always consider women as a second sex. So women are always deprived of the basic necessities of life, just like the equal rights, dignity and freedom. In the patriarchal society, women are always suppressed and oppressed by the society and it leads to the gender inequality. We define the individuals on the basis of gender. In the patriarchal system, society constructs some rule regulations and the individuals are forced to act according to the gender norms that is designed by the patriarchal society. In the patriarchal society, men are always considered as a superior one and women are always considered as an inferior one, and they think that women are weak and so on and women are exploited by the society. In the case of gender roles, both the genders plays the different roles, women are forced to deals with the household works and men are engaged with the different tasks.

This study will be engaged with the gender inequality in the Assamese novels that is represented by the novelists throughout their novels.

Key words: Gender inequality, women, men, Assamese novel, Patriarchal society.

Introduction:

Sex is biological and Gender is a socially constructed idea. Robert Stoller has explained on the word 'Gender' in his book "Sex and Gender" like this, "Gender is a term that has psychological and cultural rather than biological connotations, if the proper term for sex are 'male' and 'female' the corresponding terms for Gender are 'masculine' and 'feminine'. They are the latter may be quite independent of sex. Gender is the amount of masculinity found in a person" (Robert Stoller, p - 5). The human being and the society support the idea of gender, which is based on the biological sex that is acquired by birth. "Each society slowly transforms a male or female into a man or a woman into masculine and feminine, with different qualities, behavior patterns, role, responsibilities, rights and exceptions." (Kamala Bhasin, p-2). This socially constructed system creates societal gender inequality.

The transition of the society and civilization can help to accomplish the gender equality and dignity of both the genders. Women plays a prominent role in the human race; which helps to the

development of human being. But in the patriarchal society, it is an illusion to find a good way for the women. In the myths, the majesty of the ancient women has given the status of goddess and on the other side the women are become the objects of sexual pleasure and private property. No matter in which way we imagine the women, but they are always exploited by the society. Engles has commented on women's societal status like this, "The overthrow of mother right was the world historic defeat of the female sex. The man seized the reins in the house also, the women regarded, enthralled, the slave of. The man's use a mere instrument of breeding children." (Friedrich Engles, p - 59)

Aim of Study:

Because of the patriarchal Assamese society, gender-related notions are seen in Assamese literature even before the development of Gender study as a 'theory'. The context of the inequality in the patriarchal society is represented in the Assamese novels by the authors. The main objective of this research paper is to show the gendered discrimination in the Assamese novels that face by the women in the society in terms of gaining the equal rights and freedom.

Method by Study:

This paper is analytical and based on Survey method and descriptive method. Sources of data collection: Primary sources and secondary sources are consulted with the help of various relevant books.

Review of Literature:

The status of men and women is being observed in the Assamese book like 'Ekso Bosoror Asomiya Upanyas' edited by Nagen Thakur, 'Swarajottar Asomiya Upanyasot Nari' written by Basanta Khanikar, 'Naribad aru Asomiya upanyas' written by Govinda Prasad Sharma., 'Uttaranat Nari' edited by Lily Cheleng, 'Asomiya sahityat Nari Bhavana' edited by Junu Borah and Anuradha Sharma, 'Ekobinso sotikar Asomiya Upanyas' edited by Jayanta Dutta and Gitashree Saikia's etc.

Gender Inequality in Indian Society:

Although there are not seen any primitive roles in the ancient time that played by the father and mother but the development of the patriarchal system is begin when people started to live in a society. After the introduction of patriarchal system in the society, the inequality and the suppression of women is started. Individuals are divided on the basis of gender. Men and men are two human beings, although patriarchal society always consider women as a second sex; where women are deprived of full human rights. The society consider men as a superior being and they relate the things like determination, hard work, and so on to the male figure on the other hand society consider women as a weak one and soft hearted human creature French writer Semon De Beauvoir has said in her novel *The Second Sex*, "One is not born, but rather becomes women." (Semon De Beauvoir - p. 330) Indian patriarchal society constructs some gender roles and they considers that men are related to the productive work and earning sources and women are related to the household works and they are economically dependent on the male figure.

Although in the Vedic period, women has gained the high social status in the society but it also mention that the status of women is conjoining with the birth of the male child. In the time of Northern Vedic era and during the time of Monu Sanhitas, the position of women is

reduced. It is mentioned in *Monu Sanhita* that women are dominated by father during their childhood and accordingly by husband and son during the age of young and old. (Prafulla Narayan Baruah - p. 136) But during of the time of Ramayana and Mahabharata, women has gained the high social status and they chose their life partner by their own way. (Jyoti Prasad Saikia, p- 156).

But in the Medieval period, the position of women is reduced because of some reasons, these are the child marriage, Satidah practice, prostitution, and polygamy. But the 19th century Indian society protest against the discrimination that is faces by the women and they promote the women education and against the system of child marriage. At the end of the 20th century, the position of women is ameliorated in the social, cultural, and political field but still the women are exploited by the patriarchal society.

Gender Inequality in the Assamese Novels:

Literature is the mirror of society. The story of a particular novel reflects the societies viewpoint and represents the real picture of the society. In the novels of the most prominent novelist of Assam like, Padmanath Gohain Barua, Beena Barua, Bhabendranath Saikia, Mamani Roisom Goswami, Nirupama Bargohain, Arupa Patangiya Kalita, Anuradha Shama Pujari etc we find the concept of gender inequality.

The individuality of women is ignored by the patriarchal society. The desire of women is controlled by the male figure. In the novel *Bhanumati* by Padmanath Gohain Barua, the marriage of Bhanumati is decided by her father without her own opinion. In the novel *Rohdoi Ligiri* by Rajinikanth Bordoloi mention that how the beauty of Rohdoi attracts the king Chandrakant Singh and she is forcefully captured by him from the side of her lover, Dayaram. The beauty of Rohdoi becomes the lust full affection of the king and this is represented through this lines. "I brought you from your parents to give them the wealth because of your beauty and I am mad at you because of your beauty." (*Moi tur rupa bhul goiye tur mak-bapekokok dhon bit di kini anisu. Moi tur rupot boliya*-Rajnikant Bordoloi's upanyas samagra, p. 598) From this it can be said that how women are became the tools of pleasure of the male. Although in this particular novel the character of Rohdoi is represented as a courageous women but she is not able to live her life by her own way.

In the novel 'Jeevaner Batat' by Birichi Kumar Baruah written with his pseudonym Beena Baruah, the protagonist of the novel Togor is married to Dharani on the decision of her father. Because in the patriarchal society, the women does not get the right of decision making. The discrimination is created to give women the role of inferior one and to impose some gender norms. After the marriage of her, she becomes the victims of domestic violence by her mother in law but she does not goes against it rather she continues her duty as a house wife.

Although Man and Woman are two humen beings but the patriarchal society consider women as a tool and ignore the individuality of women. In the novel *Antarip* by Bhabendranath Saikia, Mahikanta does not take the opinion of his first wife, Menoka in terms of his second marriage with Kiron. Because for Mahikanta, Menoka is a sexual object and the value of her is lost after the fulfilment of his sexual pleasure.

Nirupoma Borgohain's representation of women and exploitation, suppression of women is shown through her novels like, *Eparer Ghar Hiparer Ghar*, *Anya Jeevan*, *Champavati* etc. In the novel *Eparer Ghar Hiparer Ghar*, the pathetic condition of women in the patriarchal society is reflected through the characters of Rekhadi, Anjali and Pateshwari. The construction of gender roles leads to the exploitation of women which is reflected in the novel *Anya Jeevan*. And the male child is always given the importance in the house over the female one which is also depicted through this novel. The patriarchal dominance and the suppression of women is also depicted in the novel, *Champavati* by Nirupoma Borgohain. Borgohain point out that Education is the main tool through which women can come out from the boundaries that is created by the society.

Purobi Bormudoi has written the novel *Gajraj Prem Aru Bandittwato* depict the the comparison of women captivity with the domestic elephant captivity and this particular novel tries to give the way to overcome from the patriarchal dominance that the women has faced throughout their lives. In the novels *Baghsaal*, *Baghjaal Aru Manuh* also showcases the discrimination in the form of gender roles. The decision of Neel Gohain to educate Bimola is refused by the elder Gohain as elder Gohain thinks that women education is not valuable.

In the traditional conservative society, women are always faced the discrimination in terms of religion also. In the upper class Hindu society, the discrimination of women is very pathetic. In the novel *Dantaal Sati Uye Khowa Hawda* (1988) by Mamoni Roisom Goswami, set in Amrongasatra in Dakhin Kamrup has depicted the pathetic condition of the young aged widows that they have faced the discrimination construct by the upper class Hindu society. In the novel *Neelkanthi Braja* also depicts that how Saudamini has faced the obstacles in her widowhood after the death of her husband. was forced to live a widowed life after her husband's premature death. Later she has fall in love with a Christian boy but she is not able to get married because of the boundaries of the society. on, she loved a Christian boy but couldn't make him her life partner because of society's strict rules and regulations. At last she has gone against the discrimination of the society in the form of suicidal and she has committed suicide.

In the novels *Ayananta*, *Mrignavi*, *Falani* by Arupa Patongia Kalita has also reflected the gender discrimination of the society. In the novel *Ayananta*, Beena has faced the problems from her grandmother because of the horse riding, and climbing in a tree and to behave like a son. When Beena wants to goes to the schools, the grandmother slaps her. The acts of the grandmother showcases that she tries to built her like a girl. The grandmother of Beena is the supporter of patriarchy and from her point of view " Husband is the all in all for the wife, wife is nothing without her husband"(Swamiye tirir sakolu, swami nohole tirir eku nathake -Arupa Potongia Kolita, 218) In the novel *Mriganavi* by Arupa Patangia Kalita the protagonist of the novel Huntora has left her education unwillingly and get married, but after some days of their marriage, her husband is dead and she has faced the discrimination of the society. in the novel *Falani* depicts the condition of women in the slum areas.

After the 1980s although people gives importance to the development of women education, economic independence of women but women has faced some problem in their work place also by the male figure. In the novel *Hridoia Ek Vigyapan* by Anuradha Sharma Pujari has depicted that how women are exploited in the work place through work the in the field of advertisement. In the novel *Kanchan* the author has depicted the real picture of exploitation of working women through the character of Kanchan. Kanchan has faced the exploitation in the

working place after she has joined in the job because of the family background. Because of the exploitation of the male figure she has lost her memory and affected by Phycho Amnesia.

Rita Chowdhury, Aradhana Goswami, Rudrani Sharma, Manikuntala Bhattacharya, Juri Bora Borgohain has also represented the gender discrimination through their works.

Conclusion:

In the 21st century feminism is raised in the top but women has not get the equal rights just like the male. So for the development of women education is the major tool along with their economic independent. On the other hand, women should have the decision making power that they can make their decision and they should be mentally strong. For the gender neutral society, both the gender should have to gain the equal rights and they should have to change their mentality to abolish the gender discrimination from the patriarchal society.

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